

Time Management is Life Management – A Review Article

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ABSTRACT

Time is one of life's most valuable possessions, as it is something you can never get back. Subsequently, one of the most essential life skills to master is time management. After all, time management is really life management. Learning how to make every day count for something is the objective. But it takes ridding your life of procrastination and a great deal of self-discipline.

The article examines the reasons for the increasing popularity of time management. It then reviews some of the major concepts contained in the literature: efficiency, effectiveness and life goals; how to find the time; keeping a time log; time planning systems; getting organized; and how to become an effective time manager. In doing so, the concept of time management is related to the literature on stress at work.

A successful transition into young adulthood requires that a person find a balance across competing activities in order to accomplish their daily responsibilities. Taking on too much or simply not knowing how to manage time efficiently may result in stress.

Some stress in a person's life is healthy when it encourages us to find a new skill, get things done, or do something really well. But stress that goes on for a long time can negatively impact all aspects of our health. Being able to manage time and, in turn stress, is essential for a healthy body and mind.

Keywords: Time management, Stress, Relaxation, productivity, life management, time planning, self-development, coping strategies.

INTRODUCTION

The interest in time management is by no means new, and in an increasingly globalized world the problem of how to manage time was already discussed by several authors already from the 1950s. They proposed different methods how to manage time issues such as work plans (e.g. to-do lists) in order to increase time performance, but also found new ways in which people in organizations people would improve their efforts and better manage their time. For the purpose of the Wyrdin, a review of the "time management" literature will be made as an attempt to offer some theoretical foundations both to the team and the users. Interestingly enough, time cannot be managed, because it is an inaccessible factor (Roe et al., 2005). Only the way a person deals with time can be influenced. Time management can be viewed as a way of monitoring and controlling time (e.g. Eilam and Aharon, 2003). This is why it would be more accurate to speak about self-management rather than time management, because it implies the performance of multiple tasks within a certain time period. However, in the literature, the term self-management has a different meaning which is monitoring and regulating oneself, but it does not make any specific reference to techniques for monitoring time use.

There is a huge difference between high school and university when it comes to managing time and academic responsibilities. In high school, there was the kind of learning that includes an explanation of everything, in other words, from A to Z. On the other hand, when students enter university, they find out that what they learn is a lecture, that only includes superficial information, and the rest is their job to know about and explore further. Time management is a skill that every student should not only know, but

also apply. A lot of university students complain about running out of time when asked to do a certain task, they get frustrated because they are not able to make it before the deadline. On the other hand, others find enough time to meet their friends and complete their assignments with no struggle; those are whom we call excellent time managers, and who are spotted for our research. Time management is extremely important, especially when it comes to university students because it will boost their grades and enhance their productivity. However, most of the time students face problems like task aversion and uncertainty, so they start to procrastinate because they lack organizational skills. As a result, students will not be able to organize duties according to their priorities, so they get distracted easily, ending up procrastinating. As we can see, time management is quite essential to any university student, and it is one of the keys to a higher GPA.

Review of Literature

It was found out that time management plays a major role in a student's achievement along with his academic performance. This section will highlight the themes of the research studies briefly.

A. Procrastination

Procrastination, to put off doing something, especially out of habitual laziness, is a result of a cultivated habit, and it impacts everyone. A lot of students tend to procrastinate at college. According to [1], they tend to do so mainly because of task-aversion. Studying, generally, is the last thing that a student would think to do. Having all kinds of entertainment and distractions, such as video games, social networks, and heard media, would really not make students get into study. It is most likely the student's responsibility, in other words, his ability to control his passion that makes the student progress and complete his tasks. Most of the students who live in the dorms, generally, can get distracted easily [1]. If students just spent ten minutes with each person there, imagine how much time would be left for them to study, even to do anything personal. More importantly, the student's uncertainty can really affect his progression at college. Hesitation will not make a student any better [1]. A lot of students spend a huge amount of time thinking about the topic they will discuss or write about, and sometimes about the way they are going to present it, and this will certainly lead them to procrastinate. Eventually, the student's Grade Point Average (GPA) will start to decrease the more he puts

off the work. However, when he keeps delaying his work, stress will rise up and more pressure will be on the student, which will lead him to late submission and his grades will decrease [1].

B. Mastering Time Management Skills

Students in universities must learn how to manage their time effectively. Fortunately, there are many techniques that can help them do that. First, students should arrange their schedule according to their priorities, which means that they should look at the important dates, such as paper due dates and arrange them according to the size of the assignment and the date it is due, and then write them down on a calendar as a reminder note. This will make students see their whole semester a lot easier and simpler [2]. Second, students should get over any bad feelings that they might face during their educational life, and move beyond them. They should "schedule time for fun and relaxation just like they would schedule a class" [2]. Studies have shown that students get higher grades when they are in a good mood, and can get lower when they are stressed or upset. Finally, according to [2], students should take notes during class and ask the professor about anything they do not understand immediately which will save them a lot of time during learning on their own.

C. Getting Organized

Source [3] says "according to a study commissioned by the temporary employment firm Accountemps, executives waste about five weeks a year looking for lost items." Thus, there is no doubt that getting organized saves a lot of time. Nonetheless, getting organized means having your desk cleared, your papers filed, your tasks listed and your events scheduled. Furthermore, the ways to get organized or manage disorganization that are discussed in [3] include having an L or U-shaped desk, keeping a diary as well as creating a "todo" list. However, the most effective method of managing disorganization according to [3] is "ruthlessly" getting rid of what you do not need. As a result, by following these steps students will find it much easier to manage their time through organization.

D. The Relationships between Time Management and the Studies on It

Source [4] shows the relationship between time management behaviors, perceived effectiveness, and work related morale and distress in a university context. For instance, in order for students to manage

their time in a good way, they must have a clear purpose in their study, and be able to answer such questions as, “Are you clear about what is important for you to achieve in your study?” Moreover, [4] has shown that students are not able to manage their time as they do not have a clear purpose in their study, getting distracted and interrupted easily, being unorganized, and not able to plan and prioritize [4]. For example, having a clear purpose is positively correlated with perceived effectiveness and morale, and negatively correlated with distress [4]. In addition, avoiding distractions and interruptions such as procrastination correlates negatively with work related distress. On the other hand, estimating the time correctly needed for a task is positively related to perceived effectiveness. Moreover, being good at planning and prioritizing such as scheduling time and working to deadlines is also positively correlated with perceived effectiveness and work related morale [4]. Last but not least, being organized, such as maintaining a clear working place and emptying your e-mail inbox daily, is negatively correlated with perceived effectiveness, morale, or distress.

Meaning of Time Management

Time management means organizing our time efficiently. It refers to the ability to use our time well. If we have good time management skills, we are able to complete all of our projects in time, and to avoid wasting time when we could be using it for something worthwhile.

Time management refers to the practice of apportioning our time so that we get all of our tasks done. It is the process of thinking about what we need to achieve, and how much time we have to achieve it in.

Time management means scheduling an appropriate number of tasks at appropriate times, and leaving ourselves with enough time to complete those tasks to a high standard. Time management involves, therefore, spending the right amount of time on the right things. It is something we can do over relatively long or relatively short periods of time.

Good time management is not just about getting all of our work done. If we are good at managing our time, we can make sure that we use our leisure time as well as possible too. It also means leaving ourselves enough time to relax and to spend time with our loved ones.

Time management is a skill we should all develop. Whether you want to turn up on time for all of your appointments in the future, or whether you want to be able to learn a new language alongside your work schedule, there is no denying that time management is a very useful skill for people in all walks of life.

The importance of time management.

Time management is very important if we want to get the most out of life, and this article provides you with key and compelling reasons for the importance of time management.

1. Fulfilling our goals: we cannot fulfil our dreams if we do not make time to do so. Good time management enables us to ensure that we have enough time to carry out all of our projects to perfection – if necessary by dividing them into sub projects which each have their own timescale for completion.

2. Relaxing: if we manage our time well, we will have plenty of time to relax. By contrast, a poorly managed schedule is a recipe for stress and unhappiness as all of those jobs pile up around us and we do not seem to have enough time to get them all done.

3. Making time for others: time management is not just about us and our goals – it is also about using our time to connect with those that we love. You do not need to buy a person an expensive gift in order to demonstrate to them that you love and care for them: often, simply making time for that person can be a much more meaningful way of doing so.

4. Remembering that our time here is finite: do not reach the end of your life burdened with regrets about things that you wish you had done, or people that you wish you had spent more time with. Good time management will enable you to use your one, finite life on this planet to the fullest of the full.

5. Remembering that we should not be trapped by time: someone who is good at managing their time is also aware that there is more to life than time management. Spending just a minute with someone that we truly love can feel more worthwhile than spending an hour working or idling. This goes to show that, though time management is important, often it is the experiences that we have that are most

important in our lives and the emotions that we feel ourselves and provoke in others as well as the good that we do on this earth, rather than the amount of time we have.

Purpose of time management.

There are many ways that time management can help us in our lives. The behind developing time management skills are as follows:

Saving money: using time efficiently makes our work more profitable. As the saying goes, 'time is money', and in many contexts this is very literally true.

Meeting deadlines: time management is an essential skill if we want to meet our deadlines.

Achieving our goals: we can only achieve our goals if we have enough time to take all of the necessary steps towards them.

Enjoying our leisure time: when we manage our time well, we find that we have plenty of time left over to relax in.

Courtesy: it is courteous not to keep other people waiting whilst we try and finish other tasks.

Effective Time Management Techniques.

It is easy to manage time effectively when you use these techniques below.

Be realistic about what you want to achieve and how much time you have to do it in. Time management plans should always be achievable, and we should always be able to carry them out without having to cause ourselves undue amounts of stress or sleeplessness. Rather, we should feel less stressed, and sleep better, because we are managing our time so well.

Make a plan: use a diary or calendar to manage your time. Have a clear idea about what you should be doing at any given time – and make sure to add in plenty of time to relax and spend time with your loved ones alongside all of those work projects.

Prioritize: what activities are your priorities? Spending time with your family, for example? Or, perhaps studying is your current priority? Knowing what your priorities are will help you to see where you need to apportion most of your time.

Take stock regularly: pause at regular intervals to check that you are on track, and if you are not, be prepared to make some adjustments to your style of working.

Delegate tasks: working as part of a team can help you to use time efficiently. If everyone is given a task to do and everyone works on their tasks at the same time, the overall project will be completed more quickly than if you attempted to do all of the tasks single-handedly.

Do not waste time: think about all the activities that you do that waste your time (such as browsing idly on the internet) and try and cut down on them.

Remind yourself of the value of time. We all only have a fixed amount of time on the earth, and once we have used up some of our time, we cannot get it back. Staying constantly aware of this is a brilliant way to motivate yourself to use your time well.

We could all be a little bit better at time management. The handy guide above will help you to hone your time management skills.

Conclusion

Once you start to manage your time carefully, you will no doubt be surprised by how much you can achieve in a single day. And, as all of the days add up, the achievements will add up too. Managing our time well reduces the stress in our lives, and helps us to get the perfect balance of work, rest and play.

If you find time management a little difficult to start off with, then why not try making a list of all the things that you need to do. Then, sit down with your journal or your calendar and work out when you are going to get all of those things done in the coming days, weeks, or months. Make sure to set yourself realistic deadlines, and to leave yourself some time for rest and relaxation as well.

Understanding the importance of time management will help you be more productive at work, have more personal time to focus on things you value outside of work, and be healthier.

A good time management system will help you become a more effective project manager and lead a more balanced life.

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